

ESTIMATION OF BISMUTH. PART VIII. GRAVIMETRIC ANALYSIS WITH PHENYLARSONIC ACID

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With the reagent phenylarsonic acid, bismuth can be estimated up to a p_H as low as 2, and in presence of nitric acid over a p_H range of about 2 to 3, it can be separated from zinc, manganese, nickel, cobalt, alkalis, alkaline earths, etc. Zinc coprecipitates at a p_H over 3. Bismuth-manganese separation can also be undertaken in presence of ammonium acetate-acetic acid buffer without adding cyanide. The method for the separation of bismuth from lead has been recommended with a little modification to avoid tedious purification procedure.

The reagent phenylarsonic acid was used for the estimation of bismuth in presence of a large number of elements (Majumdar, this *Journal*, 1944, 21, 119, 187, 188). There bismuth could not be separated from zinc and manganese in presence of cyanide due to instability of the cyanide complexes of those two elements under the conditions of the experiments. In a subsequent paper (Majumdar, *ibid.*, 1945, 22, 313) it has been shown that bismuth can also be estimated in presence of dilute nitric and acetic acids. In this paper a study of the p_H ranges over which bismuth can be accurately estimated and, if possible, its separation from other elements at lower p_H ranges has been made. Moreover, the method suggested for the separation of bismuth from lead (Majumdar, *ibid.*, 1944, 21, 119) has been modified to avoid the tedious procedure which is time consuming because of the slow addition of ammonium acetate solution.

During this investigation it was found that bismuth could be accurately estimated up to a p_H as low as about 2, and that during a bismuth-zinc separation, zinc coprecipitates at a p_H over 3 and that bismuth could be separated from zinc, manganese, nickel, cobalt, alkalis, alkaline earths, etc. in presence of nitric acid and that bismuth could also be separated from manganese in presence of ammonium acetate-acetic acid buffer without the addition of cyanide. As phenylarsonic acid does not produce any precipitate with the salts of alkalis and alkaline earths, the estimation of bismuth may further be conducted in their presence.

EXPERIMENTAL

Reagents and Standard Solutions.—Except where specifically mentioned, the chemicals used were all of reagent quality. Reagents were (i) prepared and recrystallised phenylarsonic acid of m. p. 157°, (ii) a 10% solution of ammonium acetate in water, (iii) a 2*N*-acetic acid solution, (iv) a 65% solution of nitric acid, (v) ammonia solution prepared by passing ammonia gas through cold water.

Standard solutions of bismuth, nickel and cobalt were prepared in the same way and from the same reagents as was reported in an earlier paper (Majumdar, this *Journal*, 1944, 21, 119). Bismuth content of its standard solution was further checked by estimating as phenylarsonate (*loc. cit.*).

Metallic lead was dissolved in nitric acid and diluted with water to a definite volume and the lead content per c. c. of the solution was determined as sulphate.

A manganese nitrate solution was prepared from manganese carbonate of B. D. H. and by the pyrophosphate method its manganese content was determined from a measured quantity of the solution.

A solution of zinc nitrate was prepared from metallic zinc and the zinc content per c.c. of the solution was determined by the pyrophosphate method.

Analytical Procedure

Study of p_H ranges.—For the study of the lower p_H range over which bismuth could be completely precipitated, 5 c. c. of the standard bismuth nitrate solution were evaporated to dryness on a water-bath. The residue was dissolved by the addition of a few drops of concentrated nitric acid (65%). 1% Solution of phenylarsonic acid (10 c.c.) in water was added to the solution which was then diluted to about 250 c. c. The mixture was then heated to boiling with stirring till the precipitate became crystalline. The precipitate was filtered, washed, dried and weighed exactly according to the method reported in a previous paper (*loc. cit.*). The p_H of the filtrate from the precipitation of bismuth was measured in each test by means of the quinhydrone electrode. The results are given in Table I.

TABLE I

No.	Bi taken.	Wt. of ppt.	Bi found.	p_H .	Error.
1	0.0289 g.	0.0592 g.	0.0290 g.	4.6	+0.0001 g.
2	0.0289	0.0588	0.0288	3.43	-0.0001
3	0.0232	0.0476	0.0233	3.2	+0.0001
4	"	0.0476	0.0233	2.7	+0.0001
5	"	0.0472	0.0231	2.3	-0.0001
6	0.0289	0.0590	0.0289	2.3	Nil
7	0.0232	0.0472	0.0231	2.0	-0.0001
8	"	0.0474	0.0232	2.1	Nil
9	"	0.0474	0.0232	2.1	Nil
10	"	0.0468	0.0229	1.95	-0.0003
11	"	0.0466	0.0228	1.9	-0.0004
12	"	0.0468	0.0229	1.85	-0.0003

By varying the amounts of nitric acid (1-2 drops to 5-6 drops) used in the dissolution of the dried residue, the hydrogen-ion concentration of the solutions was varied.

Separation of Bismuth from Zinc

For the estimation of bismuth in presence of zinc from a nitric acid solution containing both the metals and free form chloride, sulphate and other interfering elements, the procedure as described above was followed. But for the study of the coprecipitation of zinc, to the nitric acid solution of metals were added a few c. c. (15-16 c. c.) of the reagent solution (1%) and the solution was neutralised with dilute ammonia, using thymol blue as indicator (acid range, 1.2 to 2.8). A few drops of dilute ammonia were then added in excess and the solution was diluted to 250 c.c., heated to boiling, etc. as mentioned above. To study the effect of different p_H , the amount of excess ammonia added was varied. Results are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

No.	Bi taken.	Zn taken.	Wt. of ppt.	Bi found.	p_H .	Error
1	0.0289 g.	0.05025 g.	0.0592 g.	0.0290 g.	...	+0.0001 g.
2	0.0289	0.05025	0.0590	0.0289	...	Nil
3	0.0289	0.1005	0.0588	0.0288	2.4	-0.0001
4	0.0289	0.1005	0.0593	0.0291	2.6	+0.0002
5	0.0232	0.15075	0.0476	0.0233	2.4	+0.0001
6	0.0232	0.15075	0.0474	0.0232	2.35	Nil
7	0.0232	0.2010	0.0474	0.0232	2.3	Nil
8	0.0232	0.2010	0.0472	0.0231	2.25	-0.0001
9	0.0232	0.3015	0.0474	0.0232	2.3	Nil
10	0.0232	0.3015	0.0474	0.0232	2.4	Nil
11	0.0232	0.05025	0.0476	0.0233	3.1	0.0001
12	0.0232	0.1005	0.0472	0.0231	3.1	-0.0001
13	0.0232	0.1005	0.1940	0.0952	4.1	+0.0720
14	0.0232	0.05025	0.0670	0.0329	3.55	+0.0097
15	0.0232	0.05025	0.0900	0.0442	3.7	+0.0210

Separation of Bismuth from Manganese, Nickel and Cobalt

Here the procedure followed was the same as has been described under the "Study of p_H ranges". Results are given in Table III.

TABLE III

No.	Metals taken.	Wt of ppt.	Bi found.	pH.	Error
1	Bi 0.0232 g. Mn 0.0408	0.0474 g.	0.0232 g.	2.2	Nil
2	Bi 0.0232 Mn 0.0408	0.0472	0.0231	2.2	-0.0001 g.
3	Bi 0.0232 Mn 0.0817	0.0474	0.0232	2.2	Nil
4	Bi 0.0232 Mn 0.0817	0.0474	0.0232	2.1	Nil
5	Bi 0.0232 Mn 0.1225	0.0474	0.0232	2.14	Nil
6	Bi 0.0232 Mn 0.1225	0.0472	0.0231	2.16	-0.0001
7	Bi 0.0232 Mn 0.1634	0.0475	0.0233	2.14	+0.0001
8	Bi 0.0232 Mn 0.1634	0.0474	0.0232	2.2	Nil
9	Bi 0.0232 Ni 0.2012	0.0474	0.0232	2.4	Nil
10	Bi 0.0232 Ni 0.1006	0.0472	0.0231	2.2	-0.0001
11	Bi 0.0232 Co 0.1140	0.0472	0.0231	2.3	-0.0001
12	Bi 0.0232 Co 0.228	0.0474	0.0232	2.2	Nil

*Separation of Bismuth from Manganese in presence of Ammonium
Acetate-acetic Acid Buffer*

After the addition of 10 to 12 c.c. of the reagent solution (1%) to the nitric acid solution of bismuth and manganese, it was neutralised with dilute ammonia (using Wesselow's indicator) and acidified with 2 c.c. of 2-N-acetic acid. Ammonium acetate solution (10 c.c., 10%) was then added to the solution which was then diluted to 250 c.c., heated to boiling etc. as described under the "Study of pH ranges". The results are given in Table IV.

TABLE IV

No.	Bi taken.	Mn taken.	Wt. of ppt.	Bi found	p _{er} cent.	Error.
1	0.0232 g.	0.0408 g.	0.0472 g.	0.0231 g.	5.0	.0001 g.
2	0.232	0.0408	0.0474	0.0232	5.1	Nil
3	0.0232	0.1225	0.0472	0.0231	4.95	-0.0001
4	0.0232	0.1634	0.0474	0.0232	5.0	Nil

Separation of Bismuth from Lead

A nitric acid solution of bismuth and lead was evaporated to dryness on a water-bath. The dried residue was dissolved by treatment with a few drops of nitric acid and to it were added 3 to 4 c.c. of a 5% solution of the reagent phenylarsonic acid. If any precipitate formed due to the addition of the reagent, that was also dissolved with the addition of a few drops of nitric acid. To this solution was then added an excess of ammonium acetate solution and diluted to 250 c.c., heated to boiling with stirring till the precipitate was crystalline. The precipitate was then filtered, washed, dried and weighed as usual (*loc. cit.*). Results are given in Table V.

TABLE V

No.	Bi taken.	Pb taken.	Ammonium acetate.	Wt. of ppt.	Bi found.	Error.
1	0.0289 g.	0.0491 g.	40 c.c.	0.0592	0.0290 g.	+0.0001 g.
2	0.0289	0.0491	50	0.0590	0.0289	Nil
3	0.0289	0.0982	50	0.0590	0.0289	Nil
4	0.0289	0.0982	50	0.0592	0.0290	+0.0001
5	0.0289	0.1473	50	0.0590	0.0289	Nil
6	0.0289	0.1473	50	0.0592	0.0290	+0.0001
7	0.0289	0.1964	50	0.0588	0.0288	-0.0001
8	0.0289	0.1964	60	0.0590	0.0289	Nil
9	0.0289	0.2946	70	0.0592	0.0290	+0.0001
10	0.0289	0.2946	70	0.0590	0.0289	Nil
11	0.0578	0.0491	50	0.1184	0.0580	+0.0002
12	0.0578	0.0491	50	0.1182	0.0580	+0.0002

C O N C L U S I O N

Phenylarsonic acid can be suitably used as a reagent for the estimation of bismuth in presence of a large number of elements. Thus, in presence of nitric acid, over the p_H range 2 to 3, bismuth can be separated from zinc, manganese, nickel, cobalt, alkalis and alkaline earths. In presence of ammonium acetate-acetic acid buffer, it was separated from alkalis, alkaline earths, lead, mercury, manganese, thallos and sulphate ions; also under the same condition it was separated from silver, copper, cadmium, cobalt and nickel using potassium cyanide as a complex forming agent. Its separation from zirconium, thorium and tin depends upon the precipitation of those metals in stronger acid solutions when bismuth phenylarsonate remains in solution.

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